

STEREOCHEMISTRY OF MONOCYCLIC RINGS. PART I. INTERCONVERSION OF METHYLCYCLOHEXANE INTO METHYLCYCLOHEPTANE RING AND SYNTHESIS OF 4-METHYLCYCLOHEPTANONE.

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4-Methylcycloheptanone has been synthesised by three different methods. Firstly 4-methylcyclohexanonecyanohydrin was converted into 4-methylcyclohexenyl cyanide which was reduced to 4-methylcyclohexylmethylamine and di-4-methylcyclohexylmethylamine. Distillation of the product obtained by the action of nitrous acid on the primary amine, yielded 4-methylcycloheptene, 4-methylcycloheptanol and 4-methylcyclohexylcarbinol. 4-Methylcycloheptanol on being oxidised gave a ketone mixture from which it has been inferred that 4-methylcycloheptanone exists in isomeric forms.

Methylsuccinic ester gave a diol on reduction which was subsequently converted into the dibromide, the di-nitrile and methyladipic acid. By the action of sodiomalonic ester on the dibromide and the subsequent hydrolysis, the corresponding suberic acid could not be obtained. The only product of this reaction was methylcyclopentane carboxylic acid. The methyladipic acid was, however, more conveniently prepared by the oxidation of 4-methylcyclohexanone. This was converted into the diol, dibromide, di-nitrile and γ -methylsuberic acid without much difficulty.

By a third method pure 4-methylcyclohexanone was converted into a mixture of ketones by the action of diazomethane by the method of Mosettig and Burger. From the ketone mixture, the semicarbazone of 4-methylcycloheptanone was isolated in fairly good yield.

It appeared to be of interest to examine the condition under which a particular ring structure can be interconverted into some other ring, the formation of which is more difficult according to Baeyer's hypothesis. Demjanow reaction provides an important experimental method for changing a lower ring system into the next higher. From the relative ease of formation of such rings, a rough estimate of the amount of strain may perhaps be made, particularly if no other factors influence such ring transformation. The preparation of substituted higher ring compounds has an added interest in that there is a possibility of isolating the necessary number of isomers if the ring system is multiplanar in character. With these ideas in view, methylcyclohexane ring was subjected to Demjanow change in order to isolate the related methylcycloheptane derivative.

The method of Ruzicka and Brugger (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1926, 9, 319) offers a possibility of transforming methylcyclohexane into a methylcycloheptane ring. Accordingly *p*-methylcyclohexanone was chosen as the first

substance to be employed, as this will not present the difficulties of forming more than one structural isomer by its ultimate transformation. Pure *p*-methylcyclohexanone was converted into the cyanohydrin (I) through the bisulphite compound and potassium cyanide, or by the direct addition of hydrogen cyanide to the free ketone. The cyanohydrin (I) was dehydrated by thionyl chloride to unsaturated nitrile (II), Ruzicka's method (*loc. cit.*) proving more satisfactory than that of Darzen (*Compt. rend.*, 1911, 152, 1601).

(I)

(II)

(III)

The reduction of the unsaturated nitrile furnished the amine (III) together with a small quantity of di-*p*-methylcyclohexylmethylamine as a by-product. The separation of these two amines was effected by distillation. The amine (III) was characterised by the formation of monobenzoyl derivative, a picrate, and other derivatives.

The primary amine (III) with nitrous acid gave a mixture of three different compounds, which were separated by careful fractional distillation. The lowest boiling fraction was the hydrocarbon (IV), while the middle fraction, which constituted the major portion of the mixture, consisted of 4-methylcycloheptanol (V). The highest fraction was obtained in very small quantity and this could not be thoroughly examined. It may perhaps be *p*-methylcyclohexylcarbinol.

(IV)

(V)

The alcohol (V), when oxidised with chromic acid, gave a ketone mixture, which yielded a semicarbazone of indefinite melting point. By careful crystallisation this was separated into two fractions, one melting at 159° and the other at 124°. The second semicarbazone (m. p. 124°) was not obtained in sufficient amount for a thorough examination. We are,

therefore, unable at present to pronounce it to be a semicarbazone of an isomeric methylcycloheptanone (VI) or that of an aldehyde obtained from *p*-methylcyclohexylcarbinol which might have been present in small quantity in the alcohol (V). The alcohol (V), however, was converted into a solid hydrogen phthalic ester and the sample used for oxidation was regenerated from the hydrogen phthalate. Therefore, we are inclined to the view that the isomeric semicarbazone could not be that of an aldehyde (VII) and is most probably an isomeric cycloheptanone. We are now investigating this point more fully.

(VI)

(VII)

In order to establish the identity of 4-methylcycloheptanone, thus prepared, it was considered necessary to synthesise the ketone. For this purpose, we at first thought that ethyl α -methylsuccinate might be reduced to the diol (VIII, R=OH). Its dibromide (VIII, R=Br) should give ethyl 3-methylhexane-1:1:6:6-tetracarboxylate (IX), which would yield γ -methyl-suberic acid on hydrolysis.

(VIII)

(IX)

But the dibromide (VIII, R=Br) gave ethyl 3-methylcyclopentane-1:1-dicarboxylate (X) exclusively with sodiomalonic ester. The product is hydrolysed to 3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid.

(X)

β -Methyladipic acid, prepared by the oxidation of *p*-methylcyclohexanone was identical with the acid obtained by the hydrolysis of the dinitrile (VIII, R=CN)-prepared from the corresponding dibromide.

Ethyl β -methyladipate furnished the diol (XI, R=OH) on reduction. This was then converted *via* the dibromo derivative to the dinitrile (XI, R=CN).

The nitrile was hydrolysed to γ -methylsuberic acid (XI, R=COOH) and thence to 4-methylcycloheptanone.

The ketone has also been prepared by the action of diazomethane on *p*-methylcyclohexanone in the presence of methyl alcohol and potassium hydroxide. During this reaction the intermediate compound (XII) changed partially into the oxide (XIII), which has not been isolated. But methylcyclooctanone was obtained in small quantity, while methylcycloheptanone (VI) was the main product of this reaction (*cf.* Mosettig and Burger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 3456). The separation of these two ketones was effected by fractional crystallisation of their semicarbazones.

The synthetic ketones, obtained by the two above described methods, yielded primarily one semicarbazone which was identical with that obtained in greater quantity from the ketone prepared by Denjanow method.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

4-Methyl-1-cyano-1-hydroxycyclohexane (I).—A solution of sodium bisulphite (104 g., 1 mol.) in water (140 c.c.), cooled in ice, was saturated with sulphur dioxide. To the ice-cold solution, *p*-methylcyclohexanone (56 g., $\frac{1}{2}$ mol.) was added gradually with continuous stirring and then left overnight. The bisulphite compound was collected, washed successively with rectified spirit and a little ether. The paste of the bisulphite compound with a little water, cooled in ice, was gradually treated with a solution of potassium cyanide (65 g.) in water (110 c.c.) with vigorous shaking. After standing for 2 hours at 0°, the oily product was filtered from the crystalline solid which was very carefully washed with ether. From the filtrate the oily

layer of cyanohydrin was separated and the aqueous solution repeatedly extracted with ether. The combined extracts were dried and the solvent was removed after the addition of a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid. The residual liquid was fractionated and the cyanohydrin collected at 65-68°/5 mm., yield 51 g. (72%). (Found: C, 68·82; H, 8·9. $C_8H_{13}ON$ requires C, 69·06; H, 9·3 per cent). This on keeping in a glass container underwent decomposition and hydrogen cyanide was slowly evolved and the decomposition was rapid in presence of ammonia.

The cyanohydrin may also be prepared by the action of hydrogen cyanide but the product is not so pure. *p*-Methylcyclohexanone (56 g., $\frac{1}{2}$ mol.) was gradually added to the liquid hydrogen cyanide (33 c.c.), cooled in a freezing mixture and then a few drops of dimethylaniline added and the mixture left overnight. After the removal of unreacted hydrogen cyanide in vacuum, the mixture was dissolved in ether, washed with a dilute solution of hydrochloric acid and after removal of the solvent, the residual oil fractionated. The first fraction consisted of unreacted ketone (4 g.) and the second fraction gave the cyanohydrin (58 g., 81%).

4-Methyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexenyl Cyanide (II).—(a) A solution of 4-methyl-1-cyano-1-hydroxycyclohexane (50 g.) in dry benzene (60 c.c.), cooled in a freezing mixture, was mixed with thionyl chloride (100 g.) dropwise with continuous stirring during 1½ hours and then left overnight. After being gently warmed on a water-bath for 2 hours, the cooled mixture was decomposed with ice-water (75 c.c.). The benzene extract of the unsaturated nitrile was washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution, dried, freed from the solvent and the residual oil fractionated, when 2·5 g. of the unreacted cyanohydrin were recovered at 65-68°/5 mm. and the unsaturated nitrile (30 g.) boiled at 98-100°/5 mm. After repeated fractionation the unsaturated nitrile was obtained as a colourless mobile liquid, which had d_4^{32} , 0·93954; n_D^{32} , 1·46898; whence $[R_L]_D$, 35·9 (calc. 36·2). (Found: C, 79·0; H, 8·8. $C_8H_{11}N$ requires C, 79·3; H, 9·0 per cent).

(b) The dehydration was also effected by Darzen's method but less satisfactorily. To a mixture of crude cyanohydrin (50 g.) in pyridine (79 g., 1·1 mol.), cooled in ice, thionyl chloride (131 g., 1·1 mol.) was added dropwise with continuous stirring during 1 hour. The dark product was heated under reflux for 1 hour, poured into water and acidified. After filtration it was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with sodium hydroxide solution (5%), dried and on repeated fractionation afforded 25 g. of the pure unsaturated nitrile.

(i) *Partial Hydrolysis of the Unsaturated Nitrile (II) to the corresponding Amide.*—To the ice-cold nitrile (2 g.) was added drop by drop ice-cold sulphuric acid (*d* 1·84, 1 c.c.) and after standing at the room temperature for 24 hours, the mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 10 hours. The thick mass after decomposition with crushed ice was extracted repeatedly with ether, the extract washed with sodium carbonate solution, dried over sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. The yellowish residue crystallised from methyl alcohol, and had m.p. 140°. (Found: C, 68·7; H, 9·1. $C_8H_{13}ON$ requires C, 69·06; H, 9·3 per cent).

(ii) The complete hydrolysis of the unsaturated nitrile to Δ^1 -tetrahydro-*p*-toluic acid was effected by heating it under reflux for 10 hours with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The acid after isolation in the usual manner crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 132–33°. (Found: C, 68·4; H, 8·5. $C_8H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 68·57; H, 8·57 per cent).

p-Methylcyclohexylmethylamine (III).—A solution of *p*-methylcyclohexenyl cyanide (20 g.) in amyl alcohol (dried over calcium) was heated to boiling and to the hot solution sodium (30 g.) was added portionwise and the reaction was allowed to proceed as vigorously as was consistent with safety. The temperature was then gradually raised to 160–70° and heating continued till all the sodium dissolved (4 hrs.). It was then allowed to cool, but while still hot, a little water (50 c.c.) was gradually introduced to prevent solidification of the mass. The solution was cooled in ice and then gradually acidified with 300 c.c. of hydrochloric acid (*d* 1·15). After removal of amyl alcohol with steam, the residual solution containing sodium chloride and the hydrochloride of the amine was evaporated to dryness on a steam-bath. The residue was powdered and treated with ether. It was then treated with an excess of well-cooled solution of potassium hydroxide (20 g.) in water (100 c.c.). The liberated amine was extracted three times with ether. The ethereal extract was dried at first over potassium hydroxide and then over anhydrous potassium carbonate. After removal of the solvent the residual liquid was fractionated. The first fraction, b.p. 67–80°/30–35 mm. (2 g.) was the unsaturated nitrile. The second fraction, which had b.p. 85–98°/34–35 mm. was a colourless liquid (10·5 g.). (Found: C, 75·9; H, 13·31. $C_8H_{17}N$ requires C, 75·6; H, 13·38 per cent). It had d_4^{21} , 0·85481; n_D , 1·45537; whence $[R_L]_D$, 40·32 (calc. 40·36).

The *benzoyl derivative* of the amine, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 93°. (Found: C, 77·4; H, 8·8. $C_{15}H_{21}ON$ requires C, 77·9; H, 9·09 per cent).

The *platinum compound*, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from rectified spirit in well defined rhombohedra, m.p. 248° (decomp.). (Found: Pt, 29·33. $C_{16}H_{34}N_2Cl_2Pt$ requires Pt, 29·36 per cent).

The *hydrochloride* crystallised from methyl alcohol in beautiful shining needles, m.p. 248-50° (with shrinking from 220° and decomposition). (Found: Cl, 21.42. $C_8H_{17}N$, HCl requires Cl, 21.7 per cent).

The third fraction, b.p. 155-165°/30-35 mm. (3 g.) probably consisted of di-*p*-methylcyclohexylmethylamine, which was obtained as a thick liquid having d_4^{25} , 0.86377; n_D^{25} , 1.45597; whence $[R_L]_D$, 74.6 (calc. 75). (Found: C, 80.5; H, 12.7. $C_{16}H_{31}N$ requires C, 81.0; H, 13.1 per cent).

4-Methylcycloheptanol and 4-Methylcycloheptene.—The solution of *p*-methylcyclohexylmethylamine (20 g.) in glacial acetic acid (11 c.c.) and water (100 c.c.) was very slowly treated with a solution of sodium nitrite (11 g.) in 12 c.c. of water. The mixture was shaken well and then heated on the steam-bath for 1½ hours with an efficient condenser through which ice-water was circulated. The brown oil separating on the surface was taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was washed with sodium carbonate solution and then with water and finally dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent the residual oil was carefully distilled and three fractions were collected: (i) b.p. 65-72°/38-40 mm. or 110-20°/90 mm. (yield 3.5 g.); (ii) b.p. 102.5°/32-35 mm. or 125-130°/90 mm. (yield 11 g.); (iii) b.p. 170-208°/14 mm. or 165-75°/7 mm. (yield 1.5 g.).

The aqueous acetate mother-liquor was made alkaline and the unreacted amine (3 g.) was regenerated.

4-Methylcycloheptene (V).—The fraction (i) was identified to be 4-methylcycloheptene. It absorbed bromine in carbon disulphide solution. It was purified by redistilling over sodium at 69-70°/38 mm. and had d_4^{21} , 0.76061; n_D^{21} , 1.42016; whence $[R_L]_D$, 36.2 (calc. 36.48). (Found: C, 87.0; H, 12.54. C_8H_{14} requires C, 87.27; H, 12.7 per cent).

γ-Methylpimelic Acid from 4-Methylcycloheptene.—The unsaturated hydrocarbon (3 g.) was oxidised with potassium permanganate (10 g.) in water (500 c.c.) by the usual method when *γ*-methylpimelic acid was obtained which, when crystallised from dry ether, had m.p. 56°. (Found: C, 54.9; H, 8.1. $C_8H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 55.17; H, 8.04 per cent).

4-Methylcycloheptanol (VI).—The second fraction, b.p. 102-105°/32-35 mm. was identified as 4-methylcycloheptanol by its conversion into the corresponding hydrogen phthalate. Equal weights of alcohol and finely powdered phthalic anhydride were mixed with little dry benzene and heated for several hours on the steam-bath under reflux. The mixture was then poured into crushed ice, sodium carbonate solution was added in slight excess and the insoluble portion removed. The filtrate was acidified with dilute sulphuric acid, extracted with ether, dried and the solid residue, obtained after removal of the solvent, was purified by several crystallisations

from light petroleum. It crystallises in silver white leaflets, m.p. 95-97°. (Found: C, 70.6; H, 7.58. $C_{16}H_{20}O_1$ requires C, 69.6; H, 7.24 per cent). It is readily soluble in alcohol or ether, sparingly soluble in light petroleum and insoluble in water. Methylcycloheptanol regenerated from the hydrogeu phthalate had, b.p. 105-106°/39-40 mm., $d_4^{31.5}$, 0.91338; n_D , 1.45737; whence $[R_L]_D$, 38.2 (calc. 38.4). (Found: C, 74.61; H, 12.49. $C_8H_{16}O$ requires C, 75.0; H, 12.5 per cent).

4-Methylcycloheptanone.—4-Methylcycloheptanol (10 g.), purified through its hydrogen phthalate, was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.) and cooled in a freezing mixture. A solution of chromic acid (6.8 g.) in water (10 c.c.) was slowly added and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 10 days at the room temperature, the mixture being shaken occasionally. It was then diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution after washing with sodium carbonate solution was dried, the solvent removed and the residue distilled and the fraction, b.p. 110-12°/55 mm. was collected. The semicarbazone of the ketone was crystallised from methyl alcohol when it melted indefinitely between 151-56°. By careful fractional crystallisation of the semicarbazone two samples were ultimately separated, one in very large proportion, m.p. 159° (sharp). (Found: C, 58.68; H, 9.14. $C_9H_{17}ON_3$ requires C, 59.01; H, 9.29 per cent) and the other in small proportion, m.p. 124°.

The ketone regenerated from the semicarbazone, m.p. 159°, possesses distinct camphoraceous odour and had d_4^{32} , 0.90178; n_D^{32} , 1.44385; whence $[R_L]_D$, 36.8 (calc. 36.95). (Found: C, 75.9; H, 10.7. $C_8H_{14}O$ requires C, 76.19; H, 11.1 per cent).

Attempt to Synthesise 4-Methylcycloheptanone.—Ethyl β methylcyano-succinate was prepared by a modification of the method of Bone and Sprankling (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 853) in better yield. Ethyl cyanoacetate (113 g., 1 mol.) was added to a well cooled solution of sodium (22 g.) in 300 c.c. of alcohol dried over calcium, when a white pasty sodium compound was formed. Ethyl α -bromopropionate (181 g., 1 mol.) was added drop by drop with vigorous stirring; the mixture being cooled all the while. The sodium compound dissolved immediately with evolution of heat and the mixture was then heated on a water-bath for 4 hours. The solution was filtered from sodium bromide and treated with a little water and the alcohol was removed in *vacuo*. The residue was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution fractionally distilled and ethyl α -cyano- β methylsuccinate collected at 125-150°/4 mm. and then redistilled at 148-50°/4 mm., yield 165 g. (70%). (Found: C, 56.08; H, 7.22. $C_{10}H_{15}O_4N$ requires C, 56.33; H, 7.04 per cent).

Methylsuccinic Acid.—Ethyl α -cyano- β -methylsuccinate (165 g.) was refluxed with 5 times its volume of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 10 hours until the whole of the oil had disappeared. On cooling no acid separated. The solution was evaporated on a water-bath to dryness and the solid residue was powdered and repeatedly extracted with ether. The acid was obtained as a solid mass and then crystallised from benzene, m.p. 112°, yield 77 g (85%).

Ethyl β -Methylsuccinate.—Methylsuccinic acid (74 g.) was esterified with absolute alcohol (294 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) for 6 hours. The ester, isolated in the usual manner, had b. p. 106°/11 mm., yield 93 g. (82%).

β -Methyl- α -butane-diol.—A solution of ethyl β -methylsuccinate (28 g.) in alcohol (200 c.c.), dried over metallic calcium, was quickly poured on to thin pieces of sodium (45 g.) from a separating funnel fitted to one arm of a Y-tube which was corked to a two litre flask. When the temperature had risen sufficiently the sodium was dispersed by shaking the contents and then the rest of alcohol (25 c.c.) was gradually poured in and the reaction allowed to proceed as vigorously as was consistent with safety. The mixture was then refluxed on an oil-bath at 140°. After addition of water (14 c.c.) the mixture was refluxed for another 30 minutes. It was then cooled in ice and hydrochloric acid (d 1.16, 207 c.c.) was gradually poured in. After the removal of sodium chloride formed, the filtrate was freed from water and acid by treatment with anhydrous potassium carbonate (225 g.). The alcoholic solution was refiltered from the solid and the latter twice washed with boiling alcohol. The combined solutions of alcohol were evaporated under reduced pressure and the residual oil fractionated. The glycol (VIII, R=OH) had b.p. 120-22°/8 mm., yield 10 g. (60%). (Found: C, 57.6; H, 11.6. $C_5H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 57.7; H, 11.5 per cent).

β -Methyl- α -dibromobutane.—Pure hydrogen bromide was passed into β -methylbutane- α -diol (22 g.) heated on an oil-bath at 140-45°. With the gradual formation of the low-boiling dibromide, the liquid began to reflux. The gas was passed (3 hours) until it began to escape freely through the condenser. The mixture was taken up in ether and the ethereal solution washed with a little bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The oil obtained from ether was fractionated and the dibromide collected at 125-28°/55 mm., yield 25 g. (63%). (Found: Br, 69.02. $C_5H_{10}Br_2$ requires Br, 69.56 per cent). It is a heavy colourless oil possessing a sharp and unpleasant odour. It gradually darkens on exposure to air and light.

Condensation of the Dibromide with Sodimalonic Ester.—To molecularised sodium (11.5 g.) and dry benzene (249 c.c.), placed in a three-necked

flask provided with a condenser, a stirrer and a tap-funnel, ethyl malonate (80 g.) was added dropwise and the mixture stirred continuously with ice-cooling. The mixture after standing in the bath for 1 hour was allowed to attain the room temperature and then heated on a water-bath for 30 minutes so as to complete the reaction. After cooling it again in ice, the dibromide (56 g.) was added drop by drop with vigorous stirring and the mixture was refluxed for 4 hours on a water-bath. The benzene solution was then washed with a little water and the aqueous layer was twice extracted with benzene. The combined benzene extracts were dried and the solvent removed in *vacuo* through a fractionating column. The almost colourless residual oil on repeated fractionation separated into two parts: one boiling at 105-115°/40-50 mm. consisting of ethyl malonate and the other at 120-22°/9-10 mm. The latter was ethyl 3-methylcyclopentane-1:1-dicarboxylate. (Found: C, 62·8; H, 8·7. $C_{12}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 63·15; H, 8·77 per cent). It is a thick colourless oil of peculiar odour.

3-Methylcyclopentane-1:1-dicarboxylic Acid.—Ethyl 3-methylcyclopentane-1:1-dicarboxylate (22·8 g.) was hydrolysed with a solution of potassium hydroxide (15 g.) in water (15 c.c.) and alcohol (45 c.c.) by refluxing for 4 hours. The acid, isolated in the usual manner, was freed from traces of oil over a porous tile and then crystallised from dry ether, m.p. 117-18° (decomp.). It is soluble in water, alcohol and ether. If the concentrated ethereal solution is allowed to evaporate spontaneously, transparent plates are obtained.

The silver salt of methylcyclopentane-dicarboxylic acid was prepared in the usual manner. (Found: Ag, 55·87. $C_8H_{10}O_4Ag_2$ requires Ag, 55·9 per cent).

3-Methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic Acid.—3-Methylcyclopentane-1:1-dicarboxylic acid (8 g.) was heated at 185-200° until the evolution of carbon dioxide had ceased. The residual oily mass was thrice distilled, b.p. 92-94°/7-8 mm., yield 3 g. It is a thick colourless oil and possesses an unpleasant odour. The silver salt of 3-methylpentamethylene-1-carboxylic acid was prepared as usual, purified and then analysed. (Found: Ag, 45·48. $C_7H_{11}O_2Ag$ requires Ag, 45·95 per cent).

β-Methyladiponitrile.—The α,δ-dibromo-β-methylbutane (10 g.) was mixed with finely powdered potassium cyanide (5·7 g.) in alcohol (50 c.c.) and was heated under reflux for 18 hours on a steam-bath. Alcohol was then removed very carefully under reduced pressure. The dinitrile was taken up in ether and the solid residue was also washed with ether. The dinitrile was then distilled at 140-145°/30-35 mm., yield 8 g. (80%). It was redistilled and had b.p. 138-40°/30 mm. (Found: C, 68·7; H, 8·05. $C_7H_{10}N_2$ requires C, 68·85; H, 8·2 per cent).

β -Methyladipic Acid.—(i) β -Methyladiponitrile (8 g.) was hydrolysed by heating with 6 times its volume of hydrochloric acid for 8 hours. The solution was cooled and the oily layer was taken up in ether, the ethereal solution was extracted with dilute sodium carbonate solution. The alkali washings together with the neutralised mother-liquor were evaporated to dryness. The residue was just acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid, cooled and extracted four times with ether. From ether a brownish black thick liquid was obtained. The last traces of hydrochloric acid were freed by evaporation of its aqueous solution four times and then it was crystallised from a mixture of dry ether and petrol (1:4), m. p. 89° .

(ii) A solution (5%) of potassium permanganate (95 g.) in water (1900 c.c.) was added slowly to 4-methylcyclohexanol (25 g.) with vigorous stirring during 24 hours and finally the solution was warmed on a steam-bath for 1 hour. When the colour of the permanaganate had disappeared the solution was filtered and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness and the residue was acidified. The solution together with the solid was extracted with ether after cooling. The residue from ether solidified on keeping in a vacuum desiccator. The acid was crystallised from a mixture of dry ether and petroleum when a crystalline solid, m. p. 90° , was obtained. From 100 g. of alcohol. 84 g. of the acid were obtained.

Ethyl β -methyladipate was prepared in the usual way and it boiled at $130\text{--}32^{\circ}/14$ mm.

3-Methylhexane-1:6-diol.—The solution of ethyl β -methyladipate (43.2 g.) in alcohol (dried over metallic calcium) (200 c.c.) was quickly poured over thin pieces of sodium (60 g.), vigorous boiling ensued at once. The mixture was then heated in an oil-bath and the remaining alcohol (400 c.c.) was introduced as quickly as was consistent with safety. The rest of the reaction was carried out under experimental conditions as described in the preparation of β -methyl- $\alpha\delta$ -butane-diol. It was obtained as a thick colourless liquid, b. p. $158\text{--}160^{\circ}/15$ mm., yield 16 g. (Found: C, 63.46; H, 11.9. $C_7H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 63.6; H, 12.1 per cent).

1:6-Dibromo-3-methylhexane.—Pure and dry hydrogen bromide was passed into the diol which was heated in an oil-bath at $140\text{--}45^{\circ}$ with a reflux arrangement. With the gradual formation of the low-boiling dibromide the oil began to boil after about $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours and the heating continued for about 3 hours. The dibromide in ether was washed successively with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and water, dried and fractionated, b.p. $145\text{--}48^{\circ}/55\text{--}60$ mm. It is a colourless mobile oil, yield 50 g. (Found: Br, 61.52. $C_7H_{14}Br_2$ requires Br, 62.01 per cent).

3-Methylsuberonitrile.—1.6-Dibromo-3-methylhexane (13 g.) was heated with finely powdered potassium cyanide (7.4 g.) in alcohol (75 c.c.) for 12 hours on a steam-bath. After removing the alcohol under reduced pressure, the residual oil was taken up in ether and the precipitated potassium bromide was thoroughly extracted with ether, the solvent was removed and the remaining oil was fractionated. A very small amount boiling at 124-26°/55 mm. was identified to be the unchanged dibromide and the second fraction, a colourless mobile liquid, b. p. 160-164°/20 mm., was the dicyanide. This was purified by repeated fractionation, yield 3 g. (Found: C, 71.8; H, 9.1. $C_8H_{14}N_2$ requires C, 72.0; H, 9.3 per cent). It had d_4^{22} , 0.9506; n_D^{22} , 1.44886; whence $[R_L]_D^{22}$, 42.67 (calc. 43).

3-Methylsuberic Acid.—3-Methylsuberonitrile (15 g.) was hydrolysed by boiling with six times its volume of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 8 hours. The thick oily mass floating on the surface was taken up in ether and the ethereal solution was extracted with sodium carbonate solution. The alkali-washings together with the neutralised mother-liquor were evaporated to dryness and the acid isolated by ether after acidification as a thick oil which solidified slowly on keeping in an evacuated desiccator. After crystallisation from dry ether it had m.p. 146°. [Found: C, 57.1; H, 8.6. M. W. (titration), 187.5. $C_8H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 57.4; H, 8.5 per cent. M. W., 188).

4-Methylcycloheptanone.—Methylsuberic acid (15 g.) was converted into calcium salt *via* its ammonium salt with slaked lime (12 g.). The solution was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and the dry mass was then intimately mixed with iron-filings (10 g.). The mixture was distilled in an atmosphere of dry nitrogen. At first the temperature was kept low when mainly water distilled over. The temperature was then gradually raised to 300-350° when a mobile brownish liquid distilled over very slowly, the operation taking about 6 hours. The oil possessed the strong odour of peppermint and gave a semicarbazone in methyl alcoholic solution.

The oily layer of the distillate was taken up in ether and the ethereal solution was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The cycloheptanone recovered from ether was distilled at 105-10°/45-50 mm. and was identified by the semicarbazone, m.p. 158-59° after several crystallisations. It did not depress the m.p. of the semicarbazone previously described.

Dry *p*-methylcyclohexanone (14 g.), purified through its bisulphite compound, was added to a solution of diazomethane (7 g.) in dry ether (450 c.c.) cooled in ice. No significant evolution of nitrogen took place even on standing for some time at 0°, but on the addition of 100 c.c. of methyl

alcohol, a vigorous evolution of nitrogen began. After two hours the reaction was almost complete and the mixture was allowed to stand at the room temperature. The nearly colourless solution became colourless after 2 days. The solution was then freed from a slight flocculent precipitate, ether was removed and the mixture of ketones was converted into semicarbazones, which melted at $140-45^{\circ}$. The non-ketonic product was taken up in ether. After repeated crystallisations from methyl alcohol the semicarbazone had m.p. $157-59^{\circ}$ and did not depress the m.p. of the semicarbazone of methylcycloheptanone described previously. The yield of the ketone by this method appears to be fairly satisfactory.

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